
ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce a new class of sets called τ^* -generalized semiclosed sets and τ^* -generalized semiopen sets in topological spaces and study some of their properties.

KEYWORDS: τ^* – *gs closed set*, τ^* – *gs open set*

INTRODUCTION

In 1970, Levine[6] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets as a generalization of closed sets in topological spaces. Using generalized closed sets, Dunham[5] introduced the concept of the closure operator cl^* and a new topology τ^* and studied some of their properties. S.P.Arya[2], P.Bhattacharyya and B.K.Lahiri[3], J.Dontchev[4], H.Maki, R.Devi and K.Balachandran[9], [10], P.Sundaram and A.Pushpalatha[12], A.S.Mashhour, M.E.Abd E1-Monsof and S.N.E1-Deeb[11], D.Andrijevic[1] and S.M.Maheshwari and P.C.Jain[9], Ivan Reilly [13], A.Pushpalatha, S.Eswaran and P.RajaRubi [14] introduced and investigated generalized semi closed sets, semi generalized closed sets, generalized semi preclosed sets, α –generalized closed sets, generalized- α closed sets, strongly generalized closed sets, preclosed sets, semi-preclosed sets and α –closed sets, generalized preclosed sets and τ^* -generalized closed sets respectively. In this paper, we obtain a new generalization of preclosed sets in the weaker topological space (X, τ^*) .

Throughout this paper X and Y are topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless otherwise explicitly stated. For a subset A of a topological space X , $int(A)$, $cl(A)$, $cl^*(A)$, $scl(A)$, $spcl(A)$, $cl_\alpha(A)$, $cl_p(A)$ and A^c denote the interior, closure, *closure**, semi-closure, semi-preclosure, α -closure, preclosure and complement of A respectively.

PRELIMINARIES

We recall the following definitions

Definition: 2.1

A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called

- (i) Generalized closed (briefly *g-closed*)[6] if $cl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is open in X
- (ii) Semi-generalized closed (briefly *sg-closed*)[3] if $scl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is semi open in X .
- (iii) Generalized semi-closed (briefly *gs-closed*)[2] if $scl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is open in X .
- (iv) α -closed[8] if $cl(int(cl(A))) \subseteq A$
- (v) α -generalized closed (briefly *ag-closed*)[9] if $cl_\alpha(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is open in X .
- (vi) Generalized α -closed (briefly *ga-closed*)[10] if $spcl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is open in X .

- (vii) Generalized semi-preclosed (briefly gsp-closed)[2] if $scl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is open in X .
- (viii) Strongly generalized closed (briefly strongly g-closed)[12] if $cl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is g-open in X .
- (ix) Preclosed[11] if $cl(int(A)) \subseteq A$
- (x) Semi-closed[7] if $int(cl(A)) \subseteq A$
- (xi) Semi-preclosed (briefly sp-closed)[1] if $int(cl(int(A))) \subseteq A$.
- (xii) Generalized preclosed (briefly gp-closed)[13] if $cl_p A \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is open.

The complements of the above mentioned sets are called their respective open sets.

Definition: 2.2

For the subset A of a topological X , the generalized closure operator cl^* [5] is defined by the intersection of all g-closed sets containing A .

Definition: 2.3

For the subset A of a topological X , the topology τ^* is defined by $\tau^* = \{G: cl^*(G^c) = G^c\}$.

Definition: 2.4

For the subset A of a topological X ,

- (i) the semi-closure of A (*briefly scl(A)*)[7] is defined as the intersection of all semi-closed sets containing A .
- (ii) the semi-Pre closure of A (*briefly spcl(A)*)[1] is defined as the intersection of all semi-preclosed sets containing A .
- (iii) the α - closure of A (*briefly cl $_{\alpha}$ (A)*)[8] is defined as the intersection of all α - closed sets containing A .
- (iv) the preclosure of A , denoted by $cl_p(A)$ [13], is the smallest preclosed set containing A .

Definition: 2.5

A subset A of a topological space X is called τ^* generalized closed set (*briefly τ^* - gclosed*)[14] if $cl^*(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is τ^* - open. The complement of τ^* - generalized closed set is called the τ^* - generalized open set (*briefly τ^* - gopen*).

Definition: 2.6

A subset A of a topological space X is called τ^* - generalized preclosed (*briefly τ^* - gp - closed*)[15] if $cl^*(cl_p(A)) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is τ^* - generalized open. The complement of τ^* - generalized preclosed set is called the τ^* - generalized preopen set (*briefly τ^* - gp - open*).

τ^* - Generalized SEMICLOSED SETS IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

In this section, we introduce the concept of τ^* - generalized semiclosed sets in topological spaces.

Definition: 3.1

A subset A of a topological space X is called τ^* - generalized semiclosed (*briefly τ^* - gsclosed*) if $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is τ^* - open. The complement of τ^* - generalized semiclosed set is called the τ^* - generalized semiopen set (*briefly τ^* - gsopen*).

Example: 3.2

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\tau = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Here (X, τ^*) is τ^* -generalized semiclosed

Theorem: 3.3

Every closed set in X is τ^* - gsclosed.

Proof:

Let A be a closed set. Let $A \subseteq G$. Since A is closed, $cl(A) = A \subseteq G$. But $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq cl(A)$. Thus, we have $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is τ^* - open. Therefore A is τ^* - gsclosed.

Theorem: 3.4

Every τ^* - closed set in X is τ^* - gsclosed.

Proof:

Let A be a τ^* -closed set. Let $A \subseteq G$ where G is τ^* -open. Since A is τ^* -closed, $cl^*(scl(A)) = A \subseteq G$. Thus, we have $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is τ^* -open. Therefore A is τ^* -gsclosed.

Theorem: 3.5

Every g-closed set in X is a τ^* -gsclosed set but not conversely.

Proof:

Let A be a g-closed set. Assume that $A \subseteq G$, G is τ^* -open in X . Then $cl(A) \subseteq G$, Since A is g-closed. But $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq cl(A)$. Therefore $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq G$. Hence A is τ^* -gsclosed.

The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example: 3.6

Consider the topological space $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Then, the set $\{a, c\}$ is τ^* -gp-closed but not g-closed.

Remark: 3.7

The following example shows that τ^* -gp-closed sets are independent from sp-closed, sg-closed set, α -closed set, preclosed set, gs-closed set, gsp-closed set, αg -closed set and $g\alpha$ -closed set.

Example: 3.8

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$ be the topological spaces.

- (i) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}, \{a, b\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ are τ^* -gs-closed but not sp-closed.
- (ii) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}$ and $\{b\}$ are sp-closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (iii) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ are τ^* -gs-closed but not sg-closed.
- (iv) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}$ and $\{b\}$ are sg-closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (v) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ are τ^* -gs-closed but not α -closed.
- (vi) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the set $\{b\}$ is α -closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (vii) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}, \{a, b\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ are τ^* -gs-closed but not preclosed.
- (viii) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the set $\{a\}$ is pre-closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (ix) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi\}$. Then the sets $\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ are τ^* -gs-closed but not gs-closed.
- (x) Consider the topology $\tau = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$. Then the sets $\{b\}, \{b, c\}$ and $\{b, d\}$ are gs-closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (xi) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the sets $\{b\}$ and $\{a, b\}$ are gsp-closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (xii) Consider the topology $\tau = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Then the set $\{a\}$ is τ^* -gs-closed but not gsp-closed.
- (xiii) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Then the set $\{a\}$ is τ^* -gs-closed but not αg -closed.
- (xiv) Consider the topology $\tau = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$. Then the set $\{b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}$ are αg -closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.
- (xv) Consider the topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Then the set $\{b\}$ is τ^* -gs-closed but not $g\alpha$ -closed.
- (xvi) Consider the topology $\tau = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$. Then the set $\{b\}, \{b, c\}$ and $\{b, d\}$ are $g\alpha$ -closed but not τ^* -gs-closed.

Theorem: 3.9

For any two sets A and B $cl^*(scl(A \cup B)) = cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B))$

Proof:

Since $A \subseteq A \cup B$, we have $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq cl^*(scl(A \cup B))$ and Since $B \subseteq A \cup B$, we have $cl^*(scl(B)) \subseteq cl^*(scl(A \cup B))$. Therefore $cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B)) \subseteq cl^*(scl(A \cup B))$. Also, $cl^*(scl(A))$ and $cl^*(scl(B))$ are the closed sets. Therefore $cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B))$ is also a closed set. Again, $A \subseteq cl^*(scl(A))$ and $B \subseteq cl^*(scl(B))$, Implies $A \cup B \subseteq cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B))$. Thus, $cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B))$ is a closed set containing $A \cup B$. Since $cl^*(scl(A \cup B))$ is the smallest closed set containing $A \cup B$. We have $cl^*(scl(A \cup B)) \subseteq cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B))$. Thus, $cl^*(scl(A \cup B)) = cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B))$

Theorem: 3.10

Union of two τ^* - *gsclosed* sets in X is a τ^* - *gsclosed* set in X .

Proof:

Let A and B be two τ^* - *gsclosed* sets. Let $A \cup B \subseteq G$, where G is τ^* - *open*. Since A and B are τ^* - *gs* - *closed* sets, $cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B)) \subseteq G$. But by theorem 3.9 $cl^*(scl(A)) \cup cl^*(scl(B)) = cl^*(scl(A \cup B))$. Therefore $cl^*(scl(A \cup B)) \subseteq G$. Hence $A \cup B$ is a τ^* - *gsclosed* set.

Theorem: 3.11

A subset A of X is τ^* - *gsclosed* if and only if $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ contains no non-empty τ^* - *closed* set in X .

Proof:

Let A be a τ^* - *gsclosed* set. Suppose that F is a non-empty τ^* - *closed* subset of $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$. Now, $F \subseteq cl^*(scl(A)) - A$. Then $F \subseteq cl^*(scl(A)) \cap A^c$, Since $cl^*(scl(A)) - A = cl^*(scl(A)) \cap A^c$. Therefore $F \subseteq cl^*(scl(A))$ and $F \subseteq A^c$. Since F^c is a τ^* -*open* set and A is a τ^* - *gsclosed*, $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq F^c$. That is $F \subseteq cl^*(scl(A)) \cap [cl^*(scl(A))]^c = \phi$. That is $F = \phi$, a contradiction. Thus, $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ contain no non-empty τ^* - *closed* set in X . Conversely, assume that $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ contains no non-empty τ^* - *closed* set. Let $A \subseteq G$, G is τ^* - *open*. Suppose that $cl^*(scl(A))$ is not contained in G . then $cl^*(scl(A)) \cap G^c$ is a non-empty τ^* - *closed* set of $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ which is a contradiction. Therefore, $cl^*(scl(A)) - A \subseteq G$ and hence A is τ^* - *gsclosed*.

Corollary: 3.12

A subset A of X is τ^* - *gsclosed* if and only $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ contains no non-empty closed set in X .

Proof:

The proof follows from the theorem 3.11 and the fact that every closed set is τ^* - *closed* set in X .

Corollary: 3.13

A subset A of X is τ^* - *gs* - *closed* if and only if $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ contains no non-empty open set in X .

Proof:

The proof follows from the theorem 3.11 and the fact that every open set is τ^* - *open* set in X .

Theorem: 3.14

If a subset A of X is τ^* - *gsclosed* and $A \subseteq B \subseteq cl^*(scl(A))$, then B is τ^* - *gsclosed* set in X .

Proof:

Let A be a τ^* - *gsclosed* set such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq cl^*(scl(A))$. Let U be a τ^* - *open* set of X such that $B \subseteq U$. Since A is τ^* - *gsclosed*, we have $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq U$.

Now, $cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq cl^*(scl(B)) \subseteq cl^*(cl^*(scl(A))) = cl^*(scl(A)) \subseteq U$.

That is $cl^*(scl(B)) \subseteq U$, U is τ^* - *open*.

Therefore B is τ^* - *gsclosed* set in X .

The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example: 3.15

Consider the topological space $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with topology $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then A and B are τ^* - *gsclosed* sets in (X, τ) . But $A \subseteq B$ is not a subset of $cl^*(scl(A))$.

Theorem: 3.16

Let A be a τ^* - *gsclosed* in (X, τ) . Then A is *g* - *closed* if and only if $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ is τ^* - *open*.

Proof:

Suppose A is g -closed in X . Then, $cl^*(scl(A)) = A$ and so $cl^*(scl(A)) - A = \phi$ which is τ^* -open in X . Conversely, suppose $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ is τ^* -open in X . Since A is τ^* - g -closed, by the theorem 3.11, $cl^*(scl(A)) - A$ contains no non-empty τ^* -closed set in X . Then, $cl^*(scl(A)) - A = \phi$. Hence, A is g -closed.

Remark 3.17

From the above discussion, we obtain the following implications.

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